

Breast Cancer Detection and Sub-typing Using Subtraction of Temporally Sequential Mammograms and Machine Learning: Assessment of Invasiveness and Tumor Grade

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Abstract—Despite significant advancements, Breast Cancer (BC) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide. The management of BC, as well as the patient prognosis, depends on the tumor invasiveness and grade. Definitive classification of both is provided by biopsy and histopathology. However, this process is both invasive and increases delays in the diagnosis. In this study, an algorithm is developed for the automatic detection and sub-typing of BC type as *in situ* vs. invasive and tumor grading as grade 2 vs. grade 3 from mammographic images and other patient data. Subtraction of temporally sequential digital mammograms and feature-based Machine Learning (ML) were combined to achieve this goal. The methodology involves two main steps: (1) detection of Regions of Interest (ROIs) and (2) classification of the ROIs. The algorithm was developed using a new dataset of 164 images, with precise annotations. Ninety-six image features and 12 epidemiological and personal history features were collected. Eight feature selection algorithms and 10 classifiers were evaluated for identifying the best models. The algorithm achieved 91.2% accuracy and 0.91 AUC for *in situ* vs. invasive classification, and 92.8% accuracy and 0.92 AUC for tumor grading. These are the first such results reported in the literature. By reducing the reliance on biopsies, the algorithm provides a faster, non-invasive, and accurate tool for the subtyping of BC. When translated to clinical practice, it has the potential to enhance diagnostic efficiency, improve patient outcomes, and lower BC-related mortality rates.

Keywords— Breast cancer, Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD), Temporal subtraction, Machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer (BC) remains a significant global health concern. The International Agency for Research on Cancer projects that by 2030, there will be 2.7 million new BC cases and 800.000 BC-related deaths globally [1]. BC can be characterized as *in situ* or invasive, depending on whether the cancer has spread beyond its original boundaries. While *in situ* carcinomas are confined to the ducts or lobules of the breast, invasive carcinomas spread beyond their original location, infiltrating the surrounding tissue [2], [3]. Accurate classification is crucial, as invasive BC requires more aggressive management [4]. Beyond classification, tumor grade is also essential in determining the prognosis and treatment strategies for BC, particularly for invasive

cases. Tumor grading is an assessment of the aggressiveness of the cancer performed by examining the morphology and proliferation rates of tumor cells under a microscope. Tumors are assigned a grade from 1 to 3 [5], with higher grades indicating a more aggressive cancer [6]. High-grade tumors are associated with poorer prognosis and a higher likelihood of metastasis [7].

Currently, the standard practice for determining the invasiveness status and tumor grade involves performing a biopsy, followed by detailed histopathological analysis [8]. However, this process is associated with significant limitations. First, there are substantial delays in obtaining the results, and patients lost in the follow-up. The American Cancer Society (ACS) affirms that the 5-year relative survival rate for localized BC is 99%, dropping to 86% for regional spread, and further to 31% for distant metastases [6]. Thus, delays can lead to narrowing the window for effective treatment, especially in cases where early start of therapy is important [5]. Another limitation is the financial burden for the healthcare systems, since the total annual cost of false positive breast biopsies exceeds \$2 billion in the United States [9]. A non-invasive method that can reliably, accurately, and instantly classify and grade BC could alleviate some of these limitations.

Mammography is an effective, non-invasive screening modality for the management of BC. Over the years, various Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems have been proposed for the diagnosis of breast abnormalities as benign or malignant, utilizing the mammographic images, Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL) techniques [10], [11]. Despite their promising performance, only one study exploited the mammograms to distinguish Ductal Carcinoma *In Situ* (DCIS) from minimally invasive BC [12]. In total, 420 patients were included, and the XGBoost model was exploited, reaching a classification accuracy of 84%. Most studies performing tumor grading depend on histopathological images [13]. Only one study (Alaekhanehshir et al., 2024), focused on tumor grading using mammograms and DL, but included only DCIS patients [14]. The study population included 464 patients, and the Area Under the receiver operating characteristics Curve (AUC) reached 0.76.

Recent results demonstrate that subtraction of temporally sequential digital mammograms can increase the diagnostic performance of BC CAD systems [15], [16]. In this study, an algorithm is proposed for the automatic classification

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Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed methodology.

Fig. 2. Example images. Case 1 (top row): Mammographic views of a 77-year-old woman with grade 2 *in situ* BC. Case 2 (bottom row): Mammographic views of a 67-year-old woman with grade 3 invasive BC. For each case: (A) Most recent mammogram in MLO view with precise annotation of a biopsy-confirmed malignant mass. (B) Most recent mammogram in CC view with precise annotations of a biopsy-confirmed malignant mass. (C) Prior normal MLO image. (D) Prior normal CC image.

of breast lesions as *in situ* vs. invasive and tumor grading as grade 2 vs. grade 3. This method involves subtraction of temporally sequential digital mammograms along with feature-based ML, a novel approach, not previously described in the literature. The algorithm was developed using a dataset of 164 images. Ninety-six image features were extracted and combined with 12 epidemiological and personal history features. They were ranked using 8 different feature selection algorithms. Ten classifiers were evaluated, along with 3 validation schemes, to effectively characterize the invasiveness and grade of each abnormality. The proposed methodology, outlined in Figure

1, achieved 91.2% and 92.8% accuracy, respectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Design and Data Collection

A new dataset was created specifically for this study, since publicly available databases lack sequential mammograms, detailed annotations, biopsy confirmations, and, in some cases, contain outdated or scanned images. The new dataset includes precise annotations of individual abnormalities, serving as the ground truth (Fig. 2). Images were collected from various screening centers across Cyprus, from women of 52 to 65 years of age. Each participant

Fig. 3. Effect of the pre-processing in a 77-year-old woman with BI-RADS breast density category *c*. (A) Original most recent image. (B) Zoomed region marked by the red square in A showing an area with a malignant mass (indicated by the arrow). (C) Zoomed region marked by the green square in A, showing an area without masses. (D) Image after CLAHE. (E) Image after gamma correction. (F) Final pre-processed image after border removal. (G) Zoomed region marked by the red square in F, showing the same area as B, after pre-processing. (H) Zoomed region marked by the green square in F, showing the same area as C, after pre-processing.

Fig. 4. Example of temporal subtraction in a 77-year-old woman with BI-RADS breast density category *c*. (A) Most recent mammogram. (B) Prior mammogram. (C) The result of subtracting the registered version of B from A. (D)-(F) Zoomed regions marked by the red squares in A-C, where the yellow squares enclose a new malignant mass that was not subtracted. The CR has increased 8 times after subtraction.

provided two mammographic views, Cranio-Caudal (CC) and Medio-Lateral Oblique (MLO), from two sequential screening rounds, resulting in a database of 164 images (2 rounds \times 2 views \times 41 cases). The average interval between successive screenings was \sim 2 years. Epidemiological and personal information was also collected for each participant.

The dataset included different abnormality types, such as micro-calcifications, masses, distortions, and asymmetry, providing a comprehensive representation of different breast abnormalities. Two radiologists and a breast surgeon evaluated the images and annotated the abnormalities as benign or suspicious. Suspicious cases were further evaluated with biopsy followed by histopathological analysis, that provided the tumor type and grade. In all cases, biopsy-confirmed malignancies were identified during the most recent screening, while prior mammograms were normal. Out of the 41 cases, 29 were diagnosed as invasive BC, while the remaining 11 were classified as *in situ* BC.

Tumor grading identified 24 cases as grade 2 and 17 as grade 3. This dataset is typical of real-world scenarios where grade 1 cancers are very rare at the time of presentation.

B. Segmentation of Regions Of Interest (ROIs)

Pre-processing steps applied to the mammograms (Fig. 3) included: (i) normalization, to adjust the pixel intensity values and (ii) filtering with (a) Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [17], (b) gamma correction [18], and (c) border removal [19]. CLAHE was applied using [8,8] tiles to readjust the gray levels within the images. Gamma correction was employed to remap pixel intensities, with the gamma parameter (γ) set to 2, and finally, border removal was performed to eliminate high-intensity areas connected to the periphery, primarily targeting the pectoral muscle.

For successful subtraction, accurate registration between recent and prior mammograms is vital to prevent artifacts.

TABLE I
FEATURE RANKINGS FOR *in situ* VS. INVASIVE BC CLASSIFICATION USING VARIOUS SELECTION TECHNIQUES, WITH THE FINAL SELECTION HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	FI-XG	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
MiAL ¹	MiAL	Area	Area	Area	MiAL	Kurtosis	Area
Solidity	Euler Number	Corr. 0 D1	MiAL	MaAL ⁶	Solidity	Contrast 0 D1	MaAL
Corr. 0 D1 ²	Corr. 0 D1	Corr. 90 D1	ED ⁵	Solidity	Corr. 0 D1	Energy 45 D1	Orientation
Corr. 45 D1	Corr. 45 D1	Corr. 135 D1	Extent	Perimeter	Corr. 45 D1	Weight	Convex Area
Corr. 90 D1	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. Mean D1	Perimeter	Contrast 45 D1	Corr. 90 D1	AC	Euler Number
Corr. 135 D1	Corr. 135 D1	Corr. 0 D2	Corr. 0 D1	Contrast 90 D1	Corr. 135 D1		ED
Corr. Mean D1	Corr. Mean D1	Corr. 45 D2	Corr. 45 D1	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. Mean D1		Solidity
Corr. STD D1	Corr. STD D1	Corr. 90 D2	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. 135 D1	Corr. STD D1		Extent
Corr. 0 D2	Corr. 90 D2	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 135 D1	Corr. Mean D1	Corr. 0 D2		Max Intensity
Corr. 45 D2	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. Mean D2	Corr. Mean D1	Corr. STD D1	Corr. 45 D2		Skewness
Corr. 90 D2	Corr. 90 D3	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 0 D2	Energy 45 D2	Corr. 90 D2		STD
Corr. 135 D2	Circularity	Corr. Mean D3	Corr. 90 D2	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 135 D2		Variance
Corr. Mean D2	Shape Ratio	Circularity	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 90 D3	Corr. Mean D2		Contrast 0 D1
Corr. 0 D3	Height	Height	Corr. Mean D2	Corr. STD D3	Corr. 0 D3		Contrast 45 D1
Corr. 45 D3	Smoking	Menarche	Corr. 90 D3	Energy 45 D3	Corr. 45 D3		Corr. 0 D1
Corr. 90 D3	AC ³	Menopause	Compactness	Circularity	Corr. 90 D3		Homogeneity 0 D1
Corr. 135 D3	Breast-feeding	Pregnancies nu.	Height	Height	Corr. 135 D3		Shape Ratio
Corr. Mean D3	Pregnancies nu.	PMH	Menopause	Menarche	Corr. Mean D3		Menopause
Circularity	PMH ⁴	Breast Density	PMH	PMH	Circularity		

¹MiAL: Minor Axis Length ²Corr.: Correlation ³AC: Alcohol Consumption ⁴PMH: Personal Medical History ⁵ED: Equivalent Diameter ⁶MaAL: Major Axis Length

TABLE II
FEATURE RANKINGS FOR TUMOR GRADING USING VARIOUS SELECTION TECHNIQUES, WITH THE FINAL SELECTION HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	FI-XG	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
Cont. 0 D1 ¹	Euler Number	Orientation	MiAL ⁷	Area	Cont. 0 D1	MaAL	MaAL
Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 135 D2	ED ⁵	Eccentricity	MaAL ⁸	Cont. 45 D1	ED	MiAL
Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 90 D3	Cont. 90 D1	Orientation	Solidity	Cont. 90 D1	Solidity	Eccentricity
Cont. 135 D1	Cont. 135 D3	Cont. 135 D1	Solidity	Skewness	Cont. 135 D1	Min Intensity	Orientation
Cont. Mean D1	Cont. Mean D3	Corr. 45 D1 ⁶	Cont. 45 D1	Kurtosis	Cont. Mean D1	Variance	Convex Area
Cont. STD D1	Energy 90 D3	Corr. 90 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Cont. STD D1	Corr. 45 D1	Filled Area
Homo. STD D1 ²	Weight	Corr. 135 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Corr. 0 D1	Homo. STD D1	Energy 45 D1	ED
Cont. 0 D2	Height	Corr. STD D1	Cont. Mean D1	Corr. 90 D1	Cont. 0 D2	Energy 135 D1	Extent
Cont. 45 D2	Smoking	Cont. 0 D2	Cont. STD D1	Corr. Mean D1	Cont. 45 D2	Energy STD D1	Mean Intensity
Cont. 90 D2	AC ⁴	Cont. 90 D2	Corr. STD D1	Homo. 45 D1	Cont. 90 D2	Homo. STD D1	Max Intensity
Cont. 135 D2	Menarche	Corr. 45 D2	Cont. 90 D2	Corr. 90 D3	Cont. 135 D2	Homo. STD D2	Skewness
Cont. Mean D2	Menopause	Age	Corr. 45 D2	Circularity	Cont. Mean D2	Homo. Mean D3	Entropy
Cont. STD D2	Breast-feeding	Weight	Corr. 135 D2	Age	Homo. 90 D2	Age	Cont. 135 D2
Cont. 0 D3	Pregnancies nu.	Height	Corr. Mean D2	Weight	Cont. 0 D3	AC	Cont. Mean D3
Cont. Mean D3	Breast Density	Menarche	Height	Menarche	Smoking	Pregnancies nu.	Weight
Smoking		Menopause	Menarche	Menopause	Menarche	Breast Density	Height
Pregnancies nu.		Pregnancies nu.	Pregnancies nu.	Breast-feeding	Pregnancies nu.		Menopause
PMH ³		PMH	PMH	Pregnancies nu.	PMH		
Breast Density		Breast Density	Breast density	Breast density	Breast Density		

¹Cont.: Contrast ²Homo.: Homogeneity ³PMH: Personal Medical History ⁴AC: Alcohol Consumption ⁵ED: Equivalent Diameter ⁶Corr.: Correlation ⁷MiAL: Minor Axis Length ⁸MiAL: Minor Axis Length

Differences in the images, between screenings, appear due to breast compression, variations in breast shape, the presence of the pectoral muscle in the MLO view, and human error during imaging [20]. Demons registration, known for its ability to account for non-linear shape deformations [21], was selected for this task. A two-stage registration was performed, consisting of overall shape and detail alignment. The registration process aligned the moving image (prior) to the fixed image (recent) by optimizing regional similarity and spatial correspondence. After registration, the prior image was subtracted from the recent one, generating a new subtracted image for further analysis (Fig. 4). Additional

processing was applied to the subtracted images using unsharp-mask filtering to enhance high spatial frequencies [22].

The segmentation process, designed to isolate the ROIs for further analysis, consisted of: (i) thresholding, (ii) application of morphological operations, and (iii) removal of peripheral pixels. Thresholding was performed to convert the image values to binary, effectively eliminating low-intensity regions corresponding to normal tissue. The threshold value was determined during training through histogram analysis and optimization of the global classification rate. Morphological operations were subsequently applied to the binary image,

Fig. 5. Results for the *in situ* vs. invasive BC classification using different classifiers and cross-validation methods.

starting with erosion, to remove isolated pixels that remained due to registration misalignments or thresholding artifacts. A 2-pixel radius was chosen. Closing operations were then utilized to consolidate neighboring pixels within potential masses, with a radius of 10 pixels, selected based on comparison with the ground truth, to ensure accurate delineation of mass constituents. Finally, high-intensity regions along the periphery of the breast, typically associated with the skin, were removed, since abnormalities do not form there. All high-intensity regions along the border were excluded. The remaining areas were considered as ROIs for subsequent analysis.

C. Feature Extraction and Selection

Some segmented ROIs represented normal regions that remained either due to misalignment during registration or tissue changes between screenings. To eliminate these regions and classify the true abnormalities, various image features were extracted from each ROI and combined with epidemiological and personal history characteristics. The images provided 96 features for each ROI, including shape-based and intensity-based characteristics, first-order statistics (FOS), and textural features using the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM). Each GLCM feature was computed at 0° , 45° , 90° , and 135° , with the mean and standard deviation (STD) calculated for each direction, resulting in 24 values for each offset distance ($D_1 = 5$, $D_2 = 15$, and $D_3 = 25$ pixels). Medical history was encoded as: 0 for negative, 1 for other diseases except cancer, 2 for other cancers, and 3 for BC. Family history was encoded as 0 for negative, 1 for other cancers, and 2 for BC. The final feature vector for each ROI contained 108 values.

To optimize the classification performance, only a subset of the features was used, selected during the training process.

Redundant features were excluded using a combination of multiple feature selection methods. These methods included: (i) t-test, (ii) Maximum Relevance-Minimum Redundancy (MRMR), (iii) Feature Importance using Extra Trees (FI-ET), (iv) Feature Importance using Random Forest (FI-RF), (v) Feature Importance using XGBoost (FI-XGB), (vi) SelectKBest, (vii) Sequential Forward Selection (SFS), and (viii) Sequential Backward Selection (SBS). Using methods (i) to (vi), a score was generated for each feature, and only the 20 features with the highest scores were further considered. SFS and SBS were used to identify the best classification performance using subsets of the selected features. A majority-rule approach was adopted to consolidate the results across all methods. Features common to at least three techniques were retained for the final feature set. Given the two classification tasks in this study, two distinct feature selection processes were performed, one tailored for each task (Table I and Table II).

As expected in real-world scenarios, the dataset was imbalanced, with uneven class distributions. Thus, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied to generate new instances for the minority class and augment the training set [23]. By oversampling the needed class, SMOTE effectively eliminated class imbalance and enhanced the robustness of the classification model.

D. Training and Comparison of Classifier Designs

Two separate binary classification procedures were performed: (i) *in situ* vs. invasive BC and (ii) grade 2 vs. grade 3 tumors. Nine classifiers were evaluated, including Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Extra Trees (ET), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), AdaBoost (ADA), Bagging (Bag), and Ensemble Voting. For

Fig. 6. Results for tumor grading using different classifiers and cross-validation methods.

k-NN, various nearest neighbor values (1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11) were tested to identify the optimal configuration. For SVM, different kernel functions, such as linear, polynomial, and radial basis function (RBF), were compared. In the Ensemble Voting method, both hard and soft voting schemes were assessed. Additionally, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) with varying architectures were tested and optimized based on validation loss and accuracy.

The classifiers were trained and tested using two validation techniques to ensure robustness: Leave-One-Patient-Out (LOPO) validation and k-fold Cross-Validation (CV), per patient, with $k = 5$ and 10. All validations were performed ensuring that data from each patient were included either in the training or test set, but not both, thereby eliminating any potential bias introduced by the presence of images from the same patient in both sets. The classification performance was assessed using sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and AUC.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Initially, selected features were used to evaluate their ability to identify the true abnormalities and eliminate falsely detected ROIs. Using LDA in a LOPO CV scheme, an accuracy of 91.1% with 0.88 AUC was achieved.

For the classification of *in situ* vs. invasive BC, 19 features selected (Table I). LDA was built with a linear discriminant criterion and no prior probabilities, k-NN with $k = 9$, SVM using an RBF kernel, and Ensemble Voting combining Decision Trees (DT), RF, ET, ADA, and Bagging in a hard voting scheme. The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy, in LOPO CV ranged between 71–88.4%, 53.6–94.6%, and 64.8–91.2% respectively (Fig. 5). The highest and most consistent performance was achieved using an ANN, which resulted in 91.2% accuracy, 88.4% sensitivity, 94.6% specificity, and an AUC of 0.91. The ANN model was

configured with 1 hidden layer containing 56 neurons and 2,410 trainable parameters. Batch normalization and adaptive dropout regularization (0.2) were applied, with Gaussian noise (0.1) being added as a regularization technique. The model was trained with the Adam optimizer, a batch size of 128, and a learning rate of 0.001, for 100 epochs.

For tumor grading, 12 features were selected (Table II). The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy, in LOPO CV ranged between 36.4–97%, 49.2–88.1%, and 50.4–92.8% respectively (Fig. 6). LDA and k-NN had the same properties as before. For the SVM classifier, a linear kernel was used, and an Ensemble Voting classifier was constructed by combining LDA, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA), k-NN, SVM, and MLP classifiers, in a hard voting scheme. Using an ANN, 92.8% accuracy, 97% sensitivity, 88.1% specificity, and an AUC of 0.92 were reached, proving the highest performance for this task. The optimized ANN architecture was the same as before. Both classification tasks were evaluated using k-fold CV with 5-fold and 10-fold splits, per patient. The algorithm demonstrated consistent performance across both k-fold settings, indicating its robustness and reliability (Fig. 5 & 6).

IV. DISCUSSION

The extensive feature selection process, outlined above, identified the most critical features for each classification task. For the *in situ* vs. invasive classification, the majority of selected features were image-based, with only 2 epidemiological characteristics being significant. In contrast, for tumor grading, out of the 12 selected features, only 4 were image-based, while the remaining 8 were epidemiological. This difference highlights the importance of tailored feature selection, depending on the specific classification task.

For the classification of invasiveness, an ANN achieved 91.2% accuracy, using LOPO CV. For tumor grading, 92.8% accuracy was reached, using an ANN in a LOPO CV scheme. Various CV schemes were employed to assess the algorithm's robustness. A slight performance decrease was observed for higher k values, given the small number of training data. This decline underscores the need for a larger dataset while affirming the algorithm's ability to accurately classify new data.

This is the first study in which sequential mammograms are used for classification of BC type and grade, making direct comparison with other studies challenging. Differences in datasets, pre-processing methods, CV techniques, classifiers, and performance evaluation methodologies, further complicate such comparisons. However, the proposed method outperforms two other studies in the literature for *in situ* vs. invasive BC (91.2% vs. 84% in [12]) and tumor grading (0.92 vs. 0.76 AUC in [14]).

A significant limitation of this study is the relatively small and unbalanced dataset. Data collection proved to be challenging as it required two consecutive rounds of mammograms for each participant. Furthermore, if an abnormality is detected in the most recent screening, the previous screening had to be normal. Another limitation is the possible disagreement between experts when more radiologists evaluate the same mammograms.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an algorithm was proposed for the automatic classification of BC type (*in situ* vs. invasive) and tumor grading by leveraging temporal subtraction and ML. This is the only algorithm that takes into consideration sequential mammograms for the classification of cancer type and tumor grade. Its results demonstrated robust performance, achieving high accuracy rates and outperforming other approaches presented in the literature. The promising findings of this study warrant further investigation involving a larger dataset with more representative samples. Moreover, temporal subtraction will be exploited for the automatic classification of the molecular subtype of BC. Such approaches could substantially reduce the need for invasive biopsies. The translation of the algorithm into clinical practice has the potential to significantly impact BC diagnostics, improving both the efficiency of diagnosis and cost, and, ultimately, impact patient outcomes by reducing mortality rates.

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